

Across the *axes*: Faculty Perceptions of Professional Development Programmes in Higher Education

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Abstract

Faculty professional development is a multifaceted process involving various models of continuing education; it benefits from a combination of practices that foster professional autonomy and transformative learning. Formal programmes typically include structured workshops and courses, while their impact depends on their relevance to faculty teaching contexts. However, informal activities, such as peer conversations, also play a significant role in faculty learning. Thus, the literature shows that a balanced approach that blends formal and informal methods, transmissive and transformative actions, creates a more effective professional development agenda. In this context, this paper presents an exploratory case study assessing faculty members' perceptions of the different possibilities regarding professional development in Higher Education. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews with three teachers identified as key participants, as they are highly committed to their professional development, regularly taking part in a variety of training activities. The findings reveal that participants valued activities spanning the formal-informal and transmissive-transformative axes. However, their perspectives on the initiatives were shaped by two lenses: the specific characteristics of each initiative in terms of form and purpose and the profile of the teacher.

Keywords: Professional Development; Higher Education; Faculty Perceptions; Project Approaches.

1 Introduction

Effective professional learning is not necessarily limited to intentional development opportunities and activities, such as workshops or courses, but it is rather often 'situated' (Lave & Wenger, 1991) and often occurs implicitly (Eraut, 2004; Evans, 2019), in sometimes unanticipated ways, through social interaction (Evans, 2025). According to Clarke and Hollingsworth 'if we are to facilitate the professional development of teachers, we must understand the process by which teachers grow professionally and the conditions that support and promote that growth' (2002, p. 947). It is also important to have clear definition of what professional development means. Some perspectives reduce professional development activities to those which are tangible and visible and/or have a direct impact on students' outcomes. However, although it may have secondary beneficiaries (namely students), professional development conceptualisations or definitions should not be reduced to this dimension (Evans, 2019).

Given this underlying complexity, identifying faculty members' interests while seeking professional development initiatives, as well as the potential of the different possible forms and models of development, is therefore relevant to the design of evidence-based professional development programmes. In this context, we carried out an exploratory case study aiming at assessing faculty members' perceptions of different possibilities regarding professional development in Higher Education. The following sections introduce a quadrant, developed specifically for this study, to analyse faculty professional development, along with the axes that underpin it. Section 3 outlines the methodology, while Section 4 presents the results. The final sections offer a discussion of the findings and concluding remarks.

2 A Quadrant for Faculty Professional Development

Research indicate that faculty professional development is a dynamic process that encompasses a range of continuing professional development actions rather than following a single path (Kennedy, 2014; Evans, 2019; Smith & Wyness, 2024, among others). According to Middlewood and colleagues (2005) professional development can be perceived as an ongoing process of reflection and review that articulates with development planning that meets corporate, departmental and individual needs.

Smith and Wyness (2024) explored the diversity of professional development in Higher Education across 13 different international perspectives. The authors developed a systematised literature review, revealing that the composition, the design and the purpose of professional development for faculty is diverse in many aspects. Their results highlight some of the key-characteristics to be considered in professional development programmes, namely: Relatability; meaningfulness; appropriate design for the transfer of learning from theory to practice; flexibility; voluntariness; and realistic feasibility for teacher attendance. Accordingly, the authors suggest that “professional development is perceived to be more valuable when it is flexible, informal and structured in its design” (Smith & Wyness, 2024, p.18).

Considering the three features identified by Smith and Wyness (2024) (i.e. flexibility, (in)formality and structure), we propose, for this study, a framework for analysing faculty professional development, structured around two axes: formal/informal and transmissive/transformative (Figure 1 – left side). Considering the two structuring axes of the suggested quadrant, teacher professional development initiatives can be allocated to different points, considering the strictness of their structure and the nature of their purpose. Given the key characteristics of each axis, described in the following sections, Figure 1 (right side) shows an initial proposal for allocating the different activities in the quadrant. This distribution is illustrative and not intended as a final or immutable arrangement; rather, it serves as a baseline for the semi-structured interviews conducted in this study. Figure 1, while part of the literature review, stands as a contribution in its own by reflecting the authors’ interpretation and organisation of existing work.

Figure 1. A Quadrant for Faculty Professional Development (left side) and an initial proposal for allocating the different initiatives in the quadrant

2.1 The formal-informal axis

According to Friedman and Philips (2004, p. 369) the legitimacy of professional development activities is often perceived of in terms of formal training courses linked to work gaining a qualification - portable and bankable. However, learning may occur in many different sets and formats, encompassing a whole range of activities

from formal to informal: formal courses, seminars, workshops, mentorship, peer learning, co-planning, online training, communities of practice, and so on.

By framing professional development as existing along a continuum of formal-informal (Eraut, 2004; Evans, 2019), rather than as a binary of formal versus informal activities it is possible to acknowledge that professional development activities can have characteristics of both, and that professionals engage in a mix of learning experiences. Looking at professional development in this continuum implies having a clear notion of what counts as formal and informal activities of professional development. Forms of informal professional learning and development are those which

are not explicitly labelled or signposted as such, and which are consequently in danger of slipping under the radar of consideration of how people develop professionally. These forms include what is referred to as “implicit” (professional) learning or development, and which I am inclined to interpret as occurring without the learner’s or developpee’s awareness or consciousness of her/his learning or development. (Evans, 2019, p. 6)

Unlike formal learning, informal learning requires teachers to develop self-regulated learning skills, have an authentic need or internal motivation, and be offered sources for collaborative learning (Avidov-Ungar et al., 2023; Dubovi & Tabak 2020). In fact, formal professional development opportunities often focus on teaching tools, knowledge and strategies, but teacher may also have social, affective, and identity needs to be met which can be addressed by informal professional development activities (Avidov-Ungar et al., 2023). In this sense, it is possible to state that formal professional development tends to be structured, planned, and often externally mandated (e.g., workshops, training sessions, accredited courses), while informal professional development activities are more organic, self-directed, and integrated into everyday practice (e.g., collegial and informal conversations, online forums, communities of practice).

2.2 The transmissive-transformative axis

Another important way of understanding professional development is by considering the purpose of the initiatives. In this concern, Kennedy (2005; 2014) presents a framework for analysing continuing professional development models according to their goals, positioning the initiatives along a continuum that ranges from ‘transmissive’ to ‘transitional’ and ultimately to ‘transformative’. In this framework, the models are classified sequentially against the capacity for supporting teachers’ autonomy and agency. Within this context, agency – i.e, teachers’ capacity to make choices, take actions, and enact changes - is considered a central ability to teachers successfully perform their professional roles, pursuing what they value in their practice (Molla & Nolan, 2020).

The initiatives categorized as transmissive focus on teacher development through expert-led instruction, usually targeting technical aspects of the job rather than issues relating to values, beliefs and attitudes. Some examples are the training, the award-bearing and the cascade model. Within transitional models, the initiatives have the potential to align with either a transmissive or a transformative agenda. Approaches typically situated within this category include coaching and mentoring, as well as communities of practice. Finally, the transformative models present a robust relationship between theory and practice. These models aim at supporting professional autonomy and agency, focusing on the assimilation of concepts, the engagement in reflective practice, the construction of new knowledge and its application across diverse contexts (Kennedy, 2005; 2014). Besides, transformative models that support teacher agency necessitates (a) creating an empowering learning environment, and (b) problematising professional practices (Molla & Nolan, 2020).

In the transmissive-transformative spectrum, although different types of models/initiatives are arranged as a continuum of discrete categories, these may not be mutually exclusive (Boylan et al., 2023). That is, instead of

advocating for one or the other, research shows that a transformative professional development agenda is supported by combining diverse practices and conditions (Kennedy, 2014).

3 An Exploratory Case Study on Faculty Perceptions

Considering the exploratory nature of this study, we developed a qualitative case study. We understand a qualitative case study as 'an in-depth description and analysis of a bounded system' (Merriam, 2009, p. 43), which has characteristics in line with the aim of this investigation, namely: (i) it is used to search for meaning and understanding; (ii) the researcher is the primary instrument of data collection and analysis; (iii) it is an inductive investigative strategy; and (iv) the end product is richly descriptive (Merriam, 2009).

As data collection strategy to assess faculty members' perceptions, semi-structured interviews were conducted with three teachers highly committed to their professional development. All of them regularly take part in a variety of training activities (more than four times a year), leading them to be identified as key participants to this study. However, we acknowledge that the fact that all participants are highly committed to professional development might bias perceptions toward more transformative and varied experiences. Their experience in higher education is very diverse, varying from "up to 5 years" to "more than 20 years". All ethical aspects were considered with participants giving them consent to participate. Their confidentiality and anonymity were guaranteed.

The interviews were guided by a previously drawn-up script and conducted by the two researchers. The focus of the interactions was their experiences and perceptions about professional development programmes. Although the questions were open-ended, they carried an underlying assumption about the initial distribution of the different professional development initiatives within the quadrant (Figure 1), informed by the theoretical framework presented. The interviews took place online. The data were recorded and transcribed; then analysed by the authors utilizing the support of NVivo Software (version 15). It was employed the thematic analysis method (Braun & Clarke, 2006), taking the thematic oriented segments as the analytical unit. Each author has done a floating reading of the data independently and then met to discuss and define the final categories and hierarchy. All authors were involved in the coding and querying phases to analyse the qualitative data and draw evidence-based conclusions systematically. Given the purpose of this study, the excerpts were categorised according to the participants' point of view (i.e, even though the workshops were allocated towards the transmissive pole in the initially suggested distribution, they were classified as transformative when the participants described them in this way). The excerpts were included in more than one category when they were connected to both.

4 Results: How do teachers experience and perceive their professional development?

The data analysis uncovered three central categories to the understanding of the faculty members' perceptions on professional development, namely: (i) Motivations, which is related to what motivates teachers to engage in professional development activities; (ii) Reflection on the structure of the activities, which refers to explicit considerations regarding the activities formats; and (iii) Perceived effects, which refers to the perceived impact of the experiences. Table1 shows the coding system generated from the data analysis; the numbers in brackets indicate the number of references associated to each category and subcategory identified in the dataset.

Table 1. Hierarchy Table of the Coding

Category	Subcategory	Description
Motivation (15)	Practices' improvement (7)	Excerpts related to the aim of increasing the repertoire of practices or learning more about the implementation of any methodology/approach.
	Practices' Validation (6)	Excerpts related to the aim of finding ways to evaluate their own practices or validating their practice through peer-feedback.
	Theoretical learning (2)	Excerpts related to the aim of learning more about methodology/approach or finding references to inform their practice.
Reflection on the structure of the activities (27)	Formal (12)	Excerpts related to well-structured activities of professional development.
	Informal (15)	Excerpts related to non-structured activities of professional development.
Perceived effects (18)	Transmissive (1)	Excerpts that mention improvements on technical aspects of the job.
	Transformative (17)	Excerpts that mention improvements on professional autonomy and agency (i.e., engagement in reflective practice; construction and/or application of new knowledge)

Participants have indicated three main motivations to join professional development activities: To improve their teaching practices, to evaluate and/or validate their practices and to learn theory. Regarding improving their teaching practices, participants highlighted the need to enhance or refine the strategies and methods they already use, as well as the need to adapt their teaching strategies according to their students' profiles and contemporary challenges: *'[I look for] the improvement in the way I teach, some new ideas, also because the changes happen so quickly [...]' (Marianne)*. Another motivation is related with evaluating and/or validating their practices, in which professional development opportunities are perceived as a space for self-reflection, but also for confirmation their approaches effectiveness: *'and also looking for, how can I say it?, there are some practices that you intuitively adopt and you want to realise how they can be theoretically supported and also know if there is evidence related to them or not.'* (Marianne). The motivation to learn new theories is based on the strong belief that a good practice is grounded in solid theory. In this sense, participants are motivated to find theoretical models that support their pedagogical decisions, to update their knowledge and some also express an interest in conducting research regarding their own pedagogical practices: *'usually I participate [in professional development activities] to check something that I do not know yet, because the knowledge keeps increasing and I do not have time to read everything' (Amy); 'And, for example, one of the things I feel the need to do is research my own practice' (Emily)*.

When reflecting on the structure of the professional development activities, participants have recognized characteristics and contributions of formal and well-structured activities and informal and non-structured activities of professional development. It is important to refer that the participants do not engage exclusively in one or the other but move across the continuum of formal-informal professional development activities. Formal professional development activities are related with getting new information, practical orientation and allowing an immediate applicability: *'In other words, many things are actually about absorbing information and then appropriating it or not in the daily practice of teaching' (Marianne)*. This kind of activities sometimes challenges participants, since they could imply experiencing new things: *'I think that there are different things, and sometimes the activities with more structure also put me in an uncomfortable position. Why? Because I need to practice a series of things that sometimes I would prefer not to do.'* (Emily). Informal activities are characterized

by spontaneity, flexibility, and peer interaction often occurring in daily routines: *'during the lunch time or during the commuting – sometimes I give a ride to a colleague – we talk and I have many ideas with our conversations' (Marianne)*. The collaboration and sharing of practices are aspects that characterise informal activities of professional development and have a positive impact: *'but we are going to think together, we are going to look at our things, we are going to produce, we usually also have interesting outcomes that result from this sharing [among peers], from this joint reflection and, therefore, what we bring are, in essence, good practices' (Amy)*.

Finally, participants referred to perceived effects of the professional development activities mainly regarding improvements on their professional practice, which occur due to something they learned or had the opportunity to reflect on: *'often we come up with an idea that we can also implement and, for example, the last time I took part [in a course] and changed a project, I was doing one workshop (...) and I had ideas for short active learning strategies, so [...] I end up introducing a more dynamic moment in the class.'* (Amy). Also, being involved in different activities (in purpose, nature, structure) of professional development allow for new ways of thinking and making connections, improving teachers' agency for choosing what suits best: *'Sometimes it's opening avenues in my brain. It's almost like being permeable to things and then, because I participate in those things, I make associations' (Emily)*.

5 Discussion: The quadrant reading lenses

These results lead to some relevant considerations regarding the design of professional development activities. First, the predominance of motivations directed primarily towards practice may be understood as a reflection of the teachers' concern with the dimension of teaching. This pattern may suggest that their engagement with professional development is closely tied to the immediate demands of their educational context, rather than abstract or theoretical pursuits. This result reinforces the need for appropriate design regarding the transfer of learning from theory to practice, highlighted by Smith and Wyness (2024).

Second, the variety of mentions regarding the different structural possibilities of professional development activities highlights teachers' intense engagement with a broad spectrum of practices. This diversity confirms that their experiences are not confined to a single approach to professional development but are instead informed by an intense contact with various kinds of activities. This exposure may foster a more flexible and adaptive understanding of professional development, enabling teachers to navigate and integrate multiple activities according to their personal and contextual needs.

Third, the presence of only a single reference to transmissive experiences may be linked to the fact that the interviewed teachers are active participants in professional development programmes. This behaviour reinforces the argument presented in the literature, where it is acknowledged that although different models and initiatives can be arranged along a continuum of discrete categories, these are not mutually exclusive (Boylan et al., 2023). As highlighted before, research demonstrates that a transformative professional development agenda benefits from combining diverse practices and conditions (Kennedy, 2014). It seems that the vast experience of the three teachers in professional development activities is reflected in the scarcity of transmissive references, that is, their commitment to their professional development has made them proficient at reflecting on their practices and beliefs and able to implement changes more autonomously, regardless of the nature of the activities they take part in.

Considering the aim of assessing faculty members' perceptions of different possibilities regarding professional development in Higher Education, this study reveals that there are highly specific factors related both to the design of each professional development activity (i.e., two workshops may be structured in very different ways) and to the individual characteristics of each participant (i.e., kind and intensity of prior experiences) that may

significantly influence one's experience with and perception on the same activity. Therefore, two lenses are needed to allocate the different professional development activities in the quadrant proposed in this study: the specific characteristics of each initiative in terms of form and purpose; and the profile of the teacher (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The Quadrant for Faculty Professional Development reading lenses

6 Conclusion: Insights for Faculty Professional Development

The complexity of the faculty professional development spectrum is based not only on the different possibilities associated with the design of the initiatives (i.e. their purposes, formats, structure, etc.), but also on the different individual characteristics, experiences, and dispositions that comprise the profile of each teacher. This interaction between the two levels (or lenses) generates so many possibilities, revealing that each process is unique. The common aspect seems to be looking for what Evans (2019; 2025) calls a 'better way' of doing things. The recognition of something as a 'better way' may occur because of a deliberate search, when an individual is dissatisfied with her/his practice and seeks improvement, but it can also occur without having been sought and without any prior recognition of deficit. However, despite what led to this 'better way', professional development activities may 'be considered dependent upon this (usually unconscious) process of comparison (between the new, "better", element of practice and what it replaces)' (Evans, 2025, p.10). In this sense, this study highlights the need to adopt two complementary lenses when designing and evaluating professional development programmes: the form and purpose of the initiative itself, and the profile of the teacher engaging with it. Each lens contributes uniquely to how the same activity can be interpreted and experienced – what may be transformative for one teacher may be perceived as transmissive or ineffective for another.

This dual perspective may carry important challenging implications for those responsible for designing and implementing professional development programmes, but it also opens new paths. Rather than focusing solely on producing 'ideal' activities, institutions should consider creating diverse, flexible opportunities with a common thread: to intentionally approach the different initiatives in an articulated way, so that each teacher can be an agent of their own development process.

Despite being exploratory in nature, this study provides a conceptual framework and empirical foundation for further investigation. However, it presents some limitations, namely the small number of interviews and the relatively homogeneous profile of the participants. Including professionals who are less engaged in

professional development activities could reveal different behaviour patterns and perspectives. Moreover, applying this framework to a larger and more diverse sample could yield more nuanced patterns, supporting the development of more tailored professional development strategies. For future research, expanding the sample size would be beneficial. Additionally, asking teachers to "fill in" the analytical framework quadrants based on their own experiences could help identify how similar or identical activities are perceived differently. This would allow for a deeper evaluation of how the two theoretical lenses operate in practice. Future studies may also explore how different institutional cultures, or disciplinary fields influence teachers' positioning within the quadrant. As institutions strive to foster teaching excellence, acknowledging the subjective, context-dependent nature of professional learning may prove essential for truly impactful development programmes.

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